

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FACTORS OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN THE MARKET COSMETICS

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ABSTRACT

This article touches on one of the pressing issues of modern marketing. The purpose of this article is to study the demand of consumers of cosmetic products and determine the factors influencing the decision-making process about the purchase of cosmetic products by students in stores in Almaty.

Today, the competition for buyers among manufacturers is intensifying, new players are appearing in the market, new products and new customer needs are appearing.

For any company, it is important to find out what is the determining factor when a client makes a decision to purchase a certain product. Marketers spend a lot of time, money and effort to find out: who are their customers? How do they make purchasing decisions? When do customers purchase the product? Where do the purchases take place? What made the customer purchase this product?

When performing the work, field (primary) and desk (secondary) research was used.

The result of the work was the development of a conditional classification of cosmetics for use in analysis; identification of the most promising groups of cosmetic products and other results (developments) that contribute to increasing the competitiveness of cosmetic companies in the future.

Keywords: cosmetic products, competition, cosmetics, questionnaires, respondents, personal needs, customer preferences, points of purchase, decision-making process.

Main part

The peculiarity of the modern market is a market in which the buyer dominates. The market also sets the proportions of consumption based on the specifically offered goods and prices. Thus, the consumer market is regulated by the supply and demand of goods, the needs and capabilities of buyers [1].

In order to understand what guides consumers when making a purchase, it is necessary to find out what influences their behavior and the purchase decision-making process.

Studying consumer behavior will allow cosmetic companies to develop effective tools and effective strategies for developing companies in order to survive in the competition for customers. Therefore, the problem raised in this article is relevant and timely.

It is necessary to take into account that the formation of the cosmetic products market in Kazakhstan and in each of its regions is not the same. The assortment varies significantly due to differences in the supply of imported goods and the lack of domestic cosmetic production. Demographic, economic and climate factors also influence the market situation. In this regard, marketing research of Almaty markets and consumer preferences in them is relevant, since it is they who provide significant

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Every society is divided into social groups or classes. Belonging to a particular social class is determined not by any single factor, such as earnings, but by a combination of occupation, income, education, material well-being and other characteristics. Consumer behavior depends quite strongly on the social class to which he belongs (choice of store, preference of brands, etc.). Social classes have their own characteristics in the awareness of needs, the choice of evaluation criteria, in the processing of information, and in the purchasing process itself.

In accordance with the above information, the income level of each category of female students is also different. How does the income factor influence the purchasing decision-making process? Respondents were asked to fill out a questionnaire with questions about the use of cosmetics [3].

Figure - 2. Distribution of respondents by level of funds for personal needs
Note: compiled by the authors

30 female students studying at higher educational institutions in Almaty, represented in different age categories and having different living conditions, took part in the survey. By determining the approximate monthly income of female students, you can find out how much money they have to purchase cosmetics. The distribution of respondents by level of funds for personal needs is shown in Figure 2.

The diagram shows that students who combine study and work have the greatest purchasing power, since the availability of wages gives them an advantage in terms of the level of funds for personal needs. Students living with their parents have limited funds for personal needs, since they take these funds from their parents.

Female students living in a dormitory (1st and 2nd year students who do not work and live away from their

parents and spend the bulk of their money on food) have the lowest level of funds for personal expenses, since they are forced to save the bulk of their money for food.

What influences the decision-making process when purchasing cosmetics? Let's consider the factor of the level of influence of various motives when making a purchase decision.

Most consumers, when purchasing cosmetics, are guided by their own knowledge [4]. Since cosmetics currently have a fairly wide spectrum of action and various methods of application, the sale of cosmetic products should be accompanied by consultations, which are trusted by a significant number of consumers (23.8%), 23.4% are guided by the latest fashion trends, commercials.

Figure 3. Structure of influence on decision-making when purchasing cosmetics

Figure 3 shows that the largest number (65%) of respondents, when purchasing cosmetics, are guided

by the advice of sales consultants. Further, the analysis showed that 44.8% of female students use personal experience and their own knowledge, more than 30%

of respondents make decisions about purchasing cosmetics under the influence of advertising. Internet resources have the least effect on the choice of cosmetics. Although recently among the population of Almaty online shopping is playing an increasingly important role.

Respondents were asked to fill out a questionnaire with questions about the use of cosmetics, and rate the importance of each of 10 consumer indicators according to the following parameters:

- important
- relatively important
- not important

Average data show that consumers consider the following indicators (in order of importance) to be very important:

1. price
2. product quality
3. efficiency
4. naturalness
5. functionality
6. brand
7. appearance (packaging)
8. innovativeness of the product

The share of respondents' main preferences for cosmetics is presented in Figure 4.

Figure - 4. Structure of respondents' main preferences for cosmetics.

The results of a study of the structure of the main preferences of female students showed that price is the main criterion when purchasing cosmetics [5]. “Important” was noted by 90% of consumers, “Relatively important” by 7.5% and “Not important” by 2.5%.

Efficiency and quality of the product - 80% of respondents rated “Important”, 7% - “Relatively important” and 3% - “Unimportant”.

The quality of a product is an important criterion for 75% of respondents, relatively important for 15%, and unimportant for 10%. Indicators of safety and naturalness, in both cases - 68%, 69% play an important role, about 22% and 25% are relatively important, and for only 10% and 6.5% of respondents - “not important”.

The following indicators are relatively important for them: appearance (packaging) - 51%, only 12% consider this indicator important, and 37% - not at all important.

The novelty of a product is an unimportant indicator for modern consumers – 71% (10.7% is important and 18.3% is relatively important).

The votes of buyers were distributed approximately equally according to the criterion “Trademark: 30% is important, 35% is relatively important, 35% is unimportant.

The data obtained can be used to improve and update the range of cosmetic skin care products.

The conducted research allowed us to obtain the following results.

The key factors influencing the decision-making process regarding the purchase of cosmetic products by students in stores in Almaty were identified.

A study of the practice of purchasing cosmetics by female students in Almaty led to the conclusion that the price factor and the income level factor play a major role when making a purchase, since most female students study full-time and have small incomes.

Of no small importance is such a factor as the consumer performance of the product.

When studying the factor of the level of influence of various motives when making a purchase decision, the most significant is the respondents’ own knowledge. Focus on the latest fashion trends and expert advice are trusted by slightly less than a quarter of respondents, respectively [6].

When determining whether a product belongs to a particular segment, students identified the following indicators in order of importance: price, efficiency and quality of the product, brand awareness. Product innovation, as the survey showed, is an unimportant indicator for modern consumers.

Focus on innovation policy allows companies to strengthen their positions in the market and provides the opportunity to earn significant profits.

A study of the influence of the factor depending on the location of the points of sale of goods showed that the majority of respondents purchase products from private sellers and bazaars, as well as from sales agents.

In terms of the frequency of purchasing cosmetics, the optimal purchase is once every three months.

The greatest demand is for hand creams, eye makeup, and face creams. And from perfumery - eau de toilette.

Brand strength continues to be relevant as an important component of a company's success in the market. The study confirmed that many purchases by female students are made based on established trust in the brand. Therefore, brand reputation has a special influence when choosing a cosmetic product. Among respondents, European brands are highly trusted. Eastern producers, mainly Korean, occupy a small share. Products from domestic producers are not in great demand.

Research has also shown that non-traditional forms of trade in cosmetics have recently become increasingly widespread in Almaty and Kazakhstan in general. Among them, online stores, trade via electronic channels via the Internet and trade with ordering goods at home are of particular importance [7].

Today, the Kazakh cosmetics market largely follows the path that the market in Western Europe has followed in its development. However, the implementation of the general laws of market development in the Kazakhstan market has its own characteristics.

We achieved our goal - we developed key factors influencing the decision-making process when students purchase cosmetic products in stores in Almaty. To achieve the goal of the study, we analyzed the market for cosmetic products in Almaty, studied the decision-making process of female students about purchasing cosmetic products, and also developed recommendations on the use of marketing tools on the decision-making process for students to purchase cosmetics.

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